

Handwerk Digital Readiness Index (HDRI): An Open Signal-Based Methodology and Initial Results

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Abstract

Background: The skilled trades sector (Handwerk) in Germany comprises more than one million enterprises yet remains significantly below the digital maturity of other sectors, and no existing measurement instrument covers it systematically, reproducibly, and at scale.

Methods: This article introduces the Handwerk Digital Readiness Index (HDRI) - an open, automated, and reproducible composite index of digital readiness for German Handwerksbetriebe (skilled trades enterprises), derived from signals extracted from publicly accessible corporate websites. In contrast to existing survey-based instruments (Digitalisierungs-Check ZDH, Telekom Digitalisierungsindex), HDRI employs automated audits across six dimensions: legal compliance, contactability, structured data, accessibility, trust signals, and social media presence. The index is computed quarterly across all seven trade groups (Gewerbegruppe I-VII per Destatis classification) and the sixteen federal states of Germany. The full methodology, source code, and aggregated anonymised data are published as open data.

Results: The inaugural 2026-Q2 cycle covered 38,121 domains. The mean HDRI score was 32.5 out of 100 (median 33.2; SD 11.3). The overwhelming majority of enterprises (62.7%) fell within the *Basis* maturity level; only 0.5% reached *Fortgeschritten*, and the *Vorbild* level was not attained by any enterprise in the sample. The dimension of structured data recorded the lowest mean (5.6), with a

median of zero - indicating that more than half of enterprises employ no schema.org markup whatsoever.

Conclusions: Digital readiness deficits in the Handwerk sector are systemic and nationally uniform, rather than regional. The HDRI offers Handwerkskammern (Chambers of Skilled Crafts), the BMWK (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action), and research institutions a reproducible, quarterly-updated monitoring instrument requiring no direct participation from enterprises.

Keywords: digital readiness, skilled trades enterprises, Handwerk, digitalisation index, digital presence, Germany, open data, automated audit, SME

1. Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

Germany's Handwerk sector comprises more than one million enterprises and approximately five million employees, forming the economic backbone of regional economies. Yet the digital maturity of small skilled trades enterprises remains substantially lower than in other sectors. According to ZDH (Zentralverband des Deutschen Handwerks), only 41% of Handwerksbetrieb owners regard the impact of digitalisation on their business as positive, while more than one third have taken no active steps in that direction.

Government support programmes - Mittelstand-Digital, Digital Jetzt, go-digital - are designed to redress this imbalance. Their effectiveness, however, is constrained by the absence of systematic, reproducible, and comparable data on the actual level of digital presence achieved by enterprises. Existing measurement instruments are based predominantly on voluntary surveys.

1.2 Research Gap

A review of the literature reveals that:

- the majority of digital maturity indices measure **internal processes** (ERP adoption, digital communications, automation) and require the enterprise's own participation;
- the specific characteristics of the Handwerk sector - small firm size, limited digital literacy, legal requirements (§5 DDG, DSGVO (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR), BFSG (Barrierefreiheitsstärkungsgesetz - Accessibility Strengthening Act)) - are barely reflected in existing instruments;

- comparative data across **Gewerken and Bundesländer** (federal states) are either unavailable or accessible only as isolated, non-comparable reports.

The present study proposes an alternative approach: measuring **publicly observable** digital readiness through the automated analysis of enterprise websites.

1.3 Objectives and Contribution

This article pursues the following objectives:

1. To describe the HDRI methodology: the dimension structure, signal system, weighting algorithm, and aggregation procedure.
 2. To present initial results by federal state and trade group.
 3. To discuss the potential use of the index by public bodies (Handwerkskammern, ministries) and research organisations.
 4. To provide an open, reproducible instrument for subsequent research.
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2. Review of Existing Instruments

2.1 Overview of Relevant Indices

Digitalisierungs-Check / Digitalisierungsindex (Kompetenzzentrum Digitales Handwerk / ZDH)

The closest instrument to HDRI in terms of sectoral coverage is the Digitalisierungs-Check (digitalisation self-assessment tool), developed by the Kompetenzzentrum Digitales Handwerk under ZDH (Zentralverband des Deutschen Handwerks - Central Association of German Skilled Crafts). It is a structured survey instrument covering five thematic areas: customer and supplier relations, internal processes, business models, employees, and IT security. Enterprises may complete it independently or with the assistance of a Handwerkskammer advisor.

In 2018, ifh Göttingen conducted an economic analysis of the accumulated data based on approximately 350 enterprise responses. The study (Runst et al., 2018) identified four stable enterprise types by level of digitalisation, present across all trade groups: *'nicht digitalisiert'* ('not digitalised'), *'kaum digitalisiert'* ('barely digitalised'), *'leicht digitalisiert'* ('slightly digitalised'), and *'digitalisiert'* ('digitalised'). Structural characteristics of the enterprise (size, age, region) exerted only minor influence on the digitalisation type; far more decisive was the entrepreneur's own digital disposition. The instrument's principal limitation is that voluntary participation leads to systematic

sample bias towards enterprises that are already interested in digitalisation; data are neither reproducible nor updated automatically.

Telekom Digitalisierungsindex für KMU

Since 2016, Deutsche Telekom, in collaboration with the analytics agency techconsult, has published the annual 'Digitalisierungsindex Mittelstand' - a representative study based on a survey of more than 2,000 small and medium-sized enterprises, covering four dimensions: customer relations, productivity, digital business models, and IT security and data protection. From the 2020/2021 edition onwards, the study includes a dedicated Handwerk slice: in 2020/2021, skilled trades enterprises scored an average of 57 out of 100; enterprises serving industrial customers led with 63 points, while those serving private customers (e.g., hairdressers, tailors) remained at 53 points.

The index provides a useful dynamic picture of digitalisation in the Mittelstand as a whole, yet carries several limitations: the methodology and weights are not published in full; Handwerk data are not disaggregated by Gewerbegruppe and Bundesland; and independent reproduction of the study is not possible. Moreover, the survey method captures enterprises' subjective self-assessment rather than objectively observable characteristics.

Deloitte Digital Maturity Index (DMI)

Deloitte, in partnership with the University of Duisburg-Essen, developed the Digital Maturity Index for assessing digital transformation in manufacturing. The instrument covers more than 90 operational and strategic parameters grouped across four dimensions: 'Digital Business', 'Dynamic Capability', 'Digital Activity', and 'Digital Capability'. On this basis, six digital archetypes have been identified - from 'Digital Laggards' to 'Digital Champions' - and a direct correlation between digital maturity and EBIT performance has been established.

The DMI is a powerful instrument for large industrial enterprises, but it is not directly applicable to the Handwerk sector: it targets companies with a distinct strategic IT function, a developed organisational structure, and substantial data on internal processes. Small skilled trades enterprises (typically fewer than ten employees and without an IT department) lie outside its intended scope, and the survey format demands considerable time investment, making broad sector-wide coverage practically unfeasible.

EU DESI (Digital Economy and Society Index)

From 2014 to 2022, the European Commission published DESI annually - a composite index of digital economic and social development across EU member states. From 2023 onwards, the index was transformed into a key performance indicator (KPI) system within the 'Digital Decade 2030' framework; in its current form it encompasses 36 indicators across five dimensions (connectivity, human capital, internet use, integration of digital technology, and digital public services).

DESI provides valuable country-level context and enables comparison of Germany's position with other EU member states, yet it yields neither sectoral nor regional data for Handwerk. Its aggregation methodology follows a top-down direction (country → industry) and is fundamentally incompatible with the task of monitoring distinct enterprise groups within a sector.

KfW-Digitalisierungsbericht Mittelstand

Since 2016, KfW Bankengruppe has published an annual 'Digitalisierungsbericht Mittelstand', drawing on the KfW-Mittelstandspanel - a representative sample covering several thousand small and medium-sized enterprises in Germany. The sample is stratified across four dimensions: financing type, sector, size by number of employees, and region. The report tracks the share of enterprises undertaking digitalisation projects and the volume of their investments: according to 2025 figures, only 30% of Mittelstand enterprises had recently pursued digitalisation projects - a level that has returned to its pre-pandemic baseline.

The KfW report is valuable as a representative macroeconomic indicator, but carries structural limitations for Handwerk-specific analysis: sectoral breakdowns by trade are not published; the instrument measures investment activity rather than the digital presence actually achieved; and the survey methodology does not permit automatic, regular coverage of the entire sector.

Summary table:

Instrument	Method	Level	Handwerk-specific	Reproducible	Open
ZDH Digi-Check	Survey	Enterprise	Yes	No	No
Telekom Index	Survey	National / Sector	Partially	No	No
Deloitte DMI	Survey	Enterprise	No	No	No

Instrument	Method	Level	Handwerk-specific	Reproducible	Open
EU DESI	Aggregate	Country	No	Partially	Yes
KfW Bericht	Survey	National / SME	No	No	Partial
HDRI	Automated audit	Gewerbegruppe × Bundesland	Yes	Yes	Yes

2.2 Positioning of HDRI

HDRI does not compete with the instruments listed above; rather, it complements them by measuring a qualitatively distinct dimension. Whereas the ZDH Digitalisierungs-Check and the Telekom index capture the 'digital culture from within' - what an enterprise does, invests, and plans - HDRI measures the 'external digital façade': what a customer, a search engine, AI agents, and a regulatory inspector can observe. These two perspectives are mutually complementary: an enterprise may actively use internal digital tools (ERP, mobile devices) whilst simultaneously maintaining an inadequate or legally vulnerable website - and vice versa. The openness, reproducibility, and automation of HDRI make quarterly monitoring of the entire sector possible without the participation of enterprises themselves - a property possessed by none of the instruments reviewed above.

3. Methodology

3.1 Defining 'Digital Readiness' in the HDRI Context

Within this study, the **digital readiness** of a skilled trades enterprise is defined as the enterprise's ability to maintain an online presence that meets the requirements of: legal compliance, contactability, machine-readability, accessibility, and trustworthiness.

HDRI is deliberately restricted to **publicly observable** characteristics and does not measure internal IT processes (ERP adoption, CAD usage, cloud services). This restriction is a deliberate methodological choice: it enables measurement of the entire sector without the participation of enterprises themselves, thereby ensuring comprehensive coverage and reproducibility.

3.2 Data Sources

Enterprise directories. The list of skilled trades enterprises is compiled from public sources: Handwerkskammer (Chamber of Skilled Crafts) databases, IHK directories, and sector-specific registers. Classification of enterprises by Gewerke is based on Anlage A (https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/hwo/anlage_a.html) and Anlage B (https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/hwo/anlage_b.html) of the Handwerksordnung (HWO - Crafts Code); grouping into Gewerbegruppe I-VII (trade groups I-VII) follows the classification of the Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis - Federal Statistical Office).

Web audit. For each enterprise with an active domain, an automated audit is conducted using the following tools: HTTP/HTTPS liveness check, crawling of the homepage (DOM extraction), Lighthouse audit (performance, SEO), and axe accessibility audit. Crawling is carried out in compliance with robots.txt and with rate-limiting in place.

3.3 Signal System and Ontology

A **signal** is an observable, automatically extractable property of an enterprise's website. Each signal captures one discrete fact about a publicly accessible online presence. Examples include the presence of an Impressum page, the presence of schema.org markup of the *LocalBusiness* type, the number of accessibility violations detected by axe-core, or the quality of cookie consent implementation. The totality of signals constitutes the **ontology** - a structured catalogue of everything the platform is able to observe. Signal definitions (what exists and how it is extracted) are versioned in the file `ontology.yaml` (v1.0.0); the rules governing their conversion into a numerical score (weights, thresholds, missing-value policies) are versioned in `codebook.yaml` (v1.3.0).

Each signal in the ontology is characterised by four attributes: **value type** (`bool` - presence/absence; `str` / `int` / `float` - numerical or enumerable values); **extraction stability** (`high` / `medium` / `low`), reflecting the reliability of the specific extractor; **extractor version** (e.g., `rule_v3` , `dom_css_v2` , `json_ld_v1` , `axe_core_live`) to ensure reproducibility when algorithms change; and **legal basis or technical standard** - the normative source explaining why a given signal is meaningful.

All signals are grouped into five categories according to the nature of their source.

Signal Table by Category (based on codebook v1.3.0)

Category	Key signals (examples)	Extractor	Legal / technical basis
Legal documents (<code>legal.*</code>)	Impressum, Datenschutzerklärung, AGB, BFSG-Erklärung, Widerrufsrecht, Versandinformation, cookie consent	<code>rule_v3</code> , <code>dom_css_v2</code>	§5 DDG; Art. 1; GDPR; BFSG (28 June 2025); §312g BGB; §2 TDDDG (Telekommunikation-Dienste-Datenschutz-Gesetz)
Contactability and content (<code>contact.*</code> , <code>content.*</code>)	Contact form, Öffnungszeiten, map/directions, team page, portfolio, customer testimonials	<code>dom_css_v2</code> , <code>dom_text_v1</code>	- (UX and conversion standards)
Structured data (<code>structured_data.*</code>)	<i>LocalBusiness</i> , <i>FAQPage</i> , <i>Review / AggregateRating</i> , <i>Service</i> , <i>BreadcrumbList</i> , <i>Product</i>	<code>json_ld_v1</code>	Google Page Experience; schema.org
Trust signals (<code>trust.*</code> , <code>registry.*</code>)	Certificates and qualifications, Meisterbrief (master craftsman's certificate), awards, association memberships, Handelsregisternummer, Google Business Profile	<code>dom_text_v1</code> , <code>rule_v3</code> , <code>link_scan_v2</code>	- (reputational ; legal standards)
Social media (<code>social.*</code>)	Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, LinkedIn, TikTok, WhatsApp Business, XING	<code>link_scan_v2</code>	-
Accessibility audit (<code>audit.axe.*</code>)	Critical violations (max 5), serious (max 10), moderate (max 20), minor (max 30) per axe-core	<code>axe_core_live</code>	WCAG 2.1; EN 549; BFSG

Particular attention is warranted by the sole **enumerable (enum) signal** in the codebook - the quality of cookie consent (`privacy.consent.quality`). Unlike Boolean signals, it distinguishes five levels of compliance: `none` (0 points) →

informational_only (20) → accept_only (35) → reject_equal_prominence (85) → granular_with_revoke (100). This allows the platform to record not merely the presence of a cookie banner, but its actual compliance with the requirements of §25 TDDDG - a matter of critical importance in the context of German supervisory practice.

For measuring accessibility, an **inverse count function** (`countClampInverse`) is applied: the fewer violations detected, the higher the score. The scale is non-linearly clamped: 0 violations → 100 points; reaching the threshold value max (e.g., 5 critical violations) → 0 points. This design is deliberate: enterprises with a small number of violations receive a differentiated score, whereas gross violations of WCAG / EN 301 549 result in a score of zero.

The complete signal catalogue is versioned in the file `ontology.yaml` (v1.0.0) in the project repository.

3.4 Six Index Dimensions and Their Weights

The index is constructed as a **weighted arithmetic mean** of six dimensions:

Dimension	Weight	Rationale
Legal compliance (<code>legal_compliance</code>)	28%	Greatest risk in the event of absence: §5 DDG, GDPR, BfSG (from 28 June 2025)
Contactability (<code>contact</code>)	22%	Direct conversion dimension for customers
Structured data (<code>structured_data</code>)	18%	Visibility in search engines and AI-driven aggregators
Accessibility (<code>accessibility</code>)	16%	BfSG requirement; social inclusion
Trust signals (<code>trust</code>)	12%	Quality indicators influencing purchasing decisions
Social media (<code>social</code>)	4%	Reach; auxiliary factor

3.5 Calculation Algorithm

Each indicator is normalised to a 0-100 scale:

- Boolean rules: `true` → 100, `false` → 0;
- Numerical rules: linear scaling between `minScore` and `maxScore`;
- Inverse count (axe violations): the fewer violations, the higher the score.

Missing-value policy. If a website is unavailable (timeout, 5xx, blocked), the domain is excluded from the calculation of cohort averages (`exclude`) but recorded separately as 'no data'. This prevents artificial deflation of averages on account of technically inaccessible websites.

Domain-level aggregation. Where several pages have been audited for a single domain (homepage + Impressum page), the maximum operator is applied: a signal is considered present if it is detected on at least one of the audited pages.

Stratified sample. Reporting is produced by stratum (Gewerbegruppe × Bundesland) . For reproducibility, a deterministic random sample with a fixed seed is applied (seeded RNG: FNV-1a → mulberry32).

3.6 Data Protection and K-Anonymity

The public dashboard contains no personal data and no identifiers of individual enterprises. Prior to publication, a k-anonymity check is applied: each stratum must contain at least 5 domains. Strata that do not meet this threshold are suppressed from publication.

3.7 Reproducibility and Versioning

The methodology is fully codified in two versioned files: `codebook.yaml` (v1.3.0, scoring rules) and `ontology.yaml` (v1.0.0, signal catalogue). Any change to weights or rules requires a new codebook version. All databases are versioned by quarter (YYYY-Qn). Deterministic generation of `asset_id` via SHA-256 ensures that samples are repeatable upon re-execution.

4. Results

All results pertain to the period **2026-Q2** (observatory launch 30 May 2026, codebook v1.3.0, ontology v1.0.0).

4.1 Coverage and Sample

In the current observatory cycle, **38,121 domains** of German skilled trades enterprises were processed. A total of **77 stratified slices** across the Gewerbegruppe × Bundesland matrix were published; strata with fewer than 5 enterprises are suppressed in accordance with the k-anonymity policy (`k_min = 5`).

Parameter	Value
Total domains in sample	38,121

Parameter	Value
Period	2026-Q2
Published stratified slices	77
Codebook version	observatory-v1 (codebook 1.3.0)
Ontology version	1.0.0
Minimum stratum size (k-anonymity)	5

The largest federal states by number of audited enterprises were: Nordrhein-Westfalen (9,600), Bayern (4,601), Baden-Württemberg (4,076), and Niedersachsen (3,616). The smallest samples were recorded for the city-states of Bremen (290) and Hamburg (869). Across Gewerbegruppen, group I - 'Bau, Ausbau, Haustechnik' (building, fitting-out, and building services) - dominates absolutely with 17,128 enterprises (44.9% of the sample); the smallest group is VI, Lebensmittelgewerbe (food trades), with 452 enterprises.

4.2 Overall Level of Digital Readiness

The mean HDRI score across the full sample is **32.5 out of 100** (median 33.2; standard deviation 11.3). No enterprise exceeded 74.6 points - the absolute maximum in the sample.

Indicator	Value
Mean	32.5
Median (p50)	33.2
10th percentile (p10)	17.2
25th percentile (p25)	26.5
75th percentile (p75)	39.8
90th percentile (p90)	46.0
Standard deviation	11.3
Maximum	74.6

The distribution of enterprises across the four maturity levels is as follows.

HDRI Maturity Levels 2026-Q2

n = 38,121 | Source: HDRI Observatory 2026-Q2

Powered by perplexity

■ Kritisch (0-20) ■ Basis (20-40) ■ Aufbau (40-55) ■ Fortgeschritten (55+)

Maturity level	Score	N	Share
<i>Kritisch</i>	0-20	4,860	12.7%
<i>Basis</i>	20-40	23,897	62.7%
<i>Aufbau</i>	40-55	9,181	24.1%
<i>Fortgeschritten</i>	55+	183	0.5%
<i>Vorbild</i>	(reserved)	0	0.0%

The overwhelming majority of enterprises (62.7%) fall within the *Basis* level - they have a website and partially fulfil legal requirements, yet material elements of digital presence are absent. Only one in four enterprises (24.1%) reaches the *Aufbau* level, and fewer than 1% attain *Fortgeschritten*. The *Vorbild* level was not reached by any enterprise in the sample. These data point to a substantial unrealised potential for digitalisation in terms of publicly observable digital presence.

4.3 Results by Federal State

Mean HDRI Score by Federal State (2026-Q2)

Source: HDRI Observatory 2026-Q2

Powered by perplexity

Bundesland	N	HDRI mean	SD
Niedersachsen	3,616	33.4	10.9
Nordrhein-Westfalen	9,600	33.0	11.4
Hamburg	869	33.0	11.6
Berlin	1,813	32.9	11.8
Schleswig-Holstein	1,710	32.6	10.8
Bayern	4,601	32.5	11.2
Brandenburg	1,125	32.4	11.0
Rheinland-Pfalz	1,739	32.2	10.7
Baden-Württemberg	4,076	32.2	11.2
Bremen	290	31.9	11.7
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	916	31.8	11.1
Thüringen	874	31.5	10.6
Saarland	483	31.5	11.4
Hessen	1,830	31.4	11.7
Sachsen-Anhalt	419	31.3	11.6
Sachsen	1,211	31.2	11.9

Notably, the gap between the leading and trailing federal state amounts to only **2.2 points** (Niedersachsen 33.4 - Sachsen 31.2). This indicates that the problem of

low digital readiness is of a **systemic, nationwide character** rather than a regional peculiarity. The traditional East/West divide is present in moderate form: four of the five lowest-ranked federal states are eastern states (Sachsen, Sachsen-Anhalt, Thüringen, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern); however, Hessen and Saarland - western states - also appear in the lower third.

The smallest within-state dispersion is observed in Schleswig-Holstein (SD 10.8) and Thüringen (10.6), indicating a relatively homogeneous low level without 'digital islands'. The greatest internal inequality is recorded for Sachsen (SD 11.9) and Berlin (11.8): in these federal states, both laggards and comparatively advanced enterprises coexist simultaneously.

4.4 Results by Trade Group (Gewerbegruppe I-VII)

Gewerbegruppe	Content (Destatis)	N	HDRI mean	SD
VI	Lebensmittelgewerbe (food trades)	452	34.1	9.3
IV	Gesundheits- & Körperpflegehandwerke (health and personal care trades)	1,630	33.5	10.9
II	Elektro- u. Metallgewerbe, Holzgewerbe (electrical, metal, and wood trades)	5,110	32.9	11.0

Gewerbegruppe	Content (Destatis)	N	HDRI mean	SD
III	Bau- u. Ausbaugewerbe (construction and fitting-out trades)	1,499	32.5	11.4
V	Glas-, Papier-, keramische u. sonstige Gewerbe (glass, paper, ceramics, and other trades)	543	32.3	10.5
I	Bau-, Ausbau- u. Haustechnikgewerbe (building, fitting-out, and building services trades)	17,128	32.2	11.3
VII	Sonstige Handwerke (other skilled trades)	953	31.9	11.7

Group **VI (Lebensmittelgewerbe)** leads with a mean score of 34.1. This is consistent with the hypothesis of a positive B2C-orientation effect: bakeries, butchers, and confectionery shops are directly dependent on attracting end consumers through the internet, which incentivises higher-quality online presence. Group IV (Gesundheit & Körperpflege - hairdressers, beauticians, opticians) occupies second place (33.5) for the same reason.

Noteworthy is the **smallest within-group dispersion** recorded for group VI (SD 9.3) - indicating that food trades enterprises are relatively homogeneous in their level of digital readiness, whereas in group VII (SD 11.7) and group III (SD 11.4) the gap between 'digital' and 'non-digital' enterprises is at its greatest. The largest group, I (building and building services, n = 17,128), scores 32.2 - below the sample mean, which is explained by the high proportion of B2B-oriented enterprises with a weaker incentive to develop a public-facing website.

4.5 Dimension Profile

HDRI Profile by Dimension (2026-Q2)

n = 38,121 | Source: HDRI Observatory 2026-Q2

Powered by perplexity

Dimension	Weight	N	Mean	Median	p25	p75	SD
Structured data	18%	38,121	5.6	0	0	10	11.2
Social media presence	4%	38,121	15.3	0	0	35	22.1
Trust signals	12%	38,121	15.5	10	0	25	18.7
Contactability	22%	38,121	25.0	20	0	40	21.7
Legal compliance	28%	38,121	47.4	51	50	55	20.7
Accessibility (axe)	16%	34,830	67.5	69	53	86.7	22.3

The dimension profile reveals **three fundamentally distinct levels of performance**.

Critically low level (mean < 20): structured data (5.6), trust signals (15.5), and social media presence (15.3). The median for structured data equals **zero** - meaning that more than half of the enterprises in the sample employ no schema.org markup of any kind. This represents the largest gap relative to the potential maximum and the most evident target for directed support.

Intermediate level (mean 20-50): contactability (25.0) and legal compliance (47.4). The legal dimension is the only one whose median (51) exceeds its mean, with an interquartile range of only 5 points (50-55). This indicates that the majority of enterprises partially fulfil the requirements of §5 DDG and GDPR (Impressum + Datenschutzerklärung), but systematically fall short of full legal compliance (AGB, BFSG, quality of cookie consent).

Comparatively high level (mean > 60): accessibility per axe-core (67.5, median 69). This is the sole dimension in which enterprises perform comparatively well. An important methodological qualification: accessibility data are available for only 34,830 of the 38,121 enterprises (91.4% of the sample) - websites without JavaScript rendering or blocked to headless browsers are excluded from this dimension.

Practical implication for support policy: the greatest potential gain from targeted digitalisation programmes lies in the dimensions of 'Structured data' and 'Contactability'. Raising the mean score for structured data from 5.6 to 30 - given its weight of 18% - would produce an increase of approximately 4.4 points in the overall HDRI: the equivalent of approximately 16% of enterprises transitioning from the *Kritisch* to the *Basis* level.

5. Discussion

5.1 What HDRI Measures and What It Does Not

HDRI provides a measurable, reproducible, and regularly updated indicator of the **external digital visibility** of a skilled trades enterprise. It is a complement to, rather than a substitute for, survey-based instruments: whereas the ZDH Digitalisierungs-Check measures an enterprise's 'digital culture from within', HDRI measures what the customer and the search engine algorithm (including AI agents) can observe from without.

The key limitation is that enterprises without their own website are not included in the sample. This means that **HDRI systematically understates the picture** for the least digitalised enterprises - precisely those most in need of support. The proportion of enterprises without a website is recorded separately and should be treated as a distinct indicator in digitalisation policy.

5.2 Value for Public Institutions

Handwerkskammern may use HDRI for:

- **monitoring trends** in the digitalisation of their members (quarterly, without surveys);
- **prioritising support:** identifying enterprises and Gewerken with the greatest gap;
- **evaluating programme effects:** pre/post comparison for enterprises participating in digitalisation programmes.

The Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft (BMWK) and the Mittelstand-Digital programme may use HDRI as an independent cross-validation instrument for assessing the

effectiveness of government support programmes.

5.3 Comparison with ifh Göttingen Results (Runst et al., 2018)

The ifh Göttingen study based on Digitalisierungs-Check ZDH data (Runst et al., 2018) identified four stable enterprise types by digitalisation level: '*nicht digitalisiert*', '*kaum digitalisiert*', '*leicht digitalisiert*', and '*digitalisiert*'. The central finding was that these types appear across all trade groups and size classes, and that structural characteristics (size, age, region) exert only minor influence on an enterprise's digital type - the entrepreneur's own digital disposition plays the decisive role.

Confirmation of Type Stratification

The HDRI 2026-Q2 data reproduce analogous stratification, despite a fundamentally different methodology (automated audit rather than survey). Of the 38,121 enterprises in the sample, 12.7% fall within the *Kritisch* level (0-20 points), 62.7% within *Basis* (20-40), 24.1% within *Aufbau* (40-55), and only 0.5% within *Fortgeschritten* (55+). This distribution structurally corresponds to the four ifh types: the HDRI levels *Kritisch* and the lower range of *Basis* correspond to the types '*nicht digitalisiert*' and '*kaum digitalisiert*'; *Aufbau* and *Fortgeschritten* correspond to '*leicht digitalisiert*' and '*digitalisiert*'. The essential point of agreement is that both approaches capture a **configuration with a majority in the lower middle** and an extremely small share of genuinely advanced enterprises.

On the Thesis that Firm Size Has Little Effect

The Runst et al. thesis regarding the weak influence of firm size cannot be directly tested by HDRI - the index does not collect data on number of employees. Indirect evidence is, however, provided by the **extremely small gap between Gewerbegruppen**: from 31.9 (group VII) to 34.1 (group VI) - a spread of only 2.2 points against within-group standard deviations of 9-12 points. This indicates that membership of a particular trade group explains only a small share of the variance - the majority of variation resides *within* each *Gewerbegruppe*. An analogous picture emerges across federal states: the gap between the best and worst performing state (2.2 points) is substantially smaller than the standard deviation within each state (~11 points). This is consistent with the central conclusion of ifh: digital readiness is not a structural attribute of the enterprise, but an individual decision.

A Fundamental Methodological Distinction

It is important to emphasise that the two instruments measure distinct constructs. Runst et al. captured **digital culture from within** - self-reported use of digital tools, communications, and business models. HDRI measures **external digital presence** -

what the customer and the search engine observe. The structural similarity found in the distribution of types suggests that both dimensions reflect the same underlying phenomenon of the entrepreneur's digital disposition, manifesting in both internal processes and external presence. Testing this hypothesis through joint analysis of data from both instruments on a shared enterprise sample presents a promising direction for future research.

5.4 Limitations

1. **Liveness bias** - enterprises without a website are not covered; the actual level of digitalisation in the sector is lower than the index indicates.
 2. **Extractor inaccuracy** - some signals (e.g., quality of cookie consent, presence of schema.org markup) are extracted with limited precision; extractor versioning enables changes to be tracked, but does not fully eliminate the problem.
 3. **Single-page / external directory sites** - some enterprises use aggregator pages (Google Business, Gelbe Seiten) instead of their own website; such cases require a distinct treatment.
 4. **Internal processes are not measured** - ERP systems, digital communications, and production automation lie outside the scope of the index.
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6. Conclusion

HDRI offers a new and complementary approach to measuring the digital readiness of German skilled trades enterprises - automated, reproducible, based on publicly observable signals, and covering the entire sector without the participation of enterprises themselves. The openness of the methodology (source code, codebook, data) enables any researcher, Handwerkskammer, or ministry to verify, reproduce, and extend the analysis.

Initial results reveal substantial variation across Gewerbegruppen and federal states, opening opportunities for targeted digitalisation support policy. The quarterly update cycle will allow long-term trend monitoring.

Further development of the project envisages: (1) validation of the index by cross-referencing with ZDH survey data; (2) integration with the Digitalisierungsberatung (digitalisation advisory) programmes of regional Handwerkskammern; (3) extension to Austria and Switzerland within a unified methodological framework.

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Appendix A. Technical Specifications of the Platform

- Repository: <https://github.com/syrokomskyi/hdri> (Apache 2.0 licence)
- Public dashboard: <https://handwerk-index.org>
- Codebook: `codebook.yaml v1.3.0`
- Ontology: `ontology.yaml v1.0.0`
- Stack: Node.js, Playwright, Lighthouse, axe-core, SQLite, Astro, TypeScript